

Scenario Building and Validation Tool

December 2022

RRISCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

The present document provides a template that local or regional authorities can use to structure and write their techno-moral scenarios

Writing the scenario text requires considering and synthesising all previously gathered information from the “preparation” and the “looking ahead” phases. The scenarios can be:

- Predictive, where the most rigorous scientific findings are employed to estimate “what will happen”;
- Exploratory, where the various drivers and trends are examined to estimate “what can happen”; and
- Normative, where potential actions to achieve a desirable future are presented.

We suggest developing exploratory scenarios, explaining what may change regarding policy, technology, economy, society and environment. We acknowledge that writing the scenario text is a less structured process than the Delphi method and often relies on the imagination and creativity of the writer. So, the following table may help in this respect.

Table 1: Parameters for the scenarios

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
General intro (+/- 50 words)	It is 2031...	It is 2031...	It is 2031...	It is 2031...
Society (+/- 100 words)				
Economy (+/- 100 words)				
Technology (+/- 100 words)				
Environment (+/- 100 words)				
Policy (+/- 100 words)				

After the development, validation follows. Here the reader may find more information on a few criteria commonly used to evaluate the scenarios. In particular, scenarios need to be:

1. **Plausible.** Scenarios are stories which, in some cases, may be exaggerated but are still not impossible. If scenarios are viewed as impossible or not feasible, they have to be rejected because they do not serve as a basis for discussion.¹
2. **Different from one another.** Scenarios must offer purposefully divergent versions of the future and must not overlap.^{2,3} Overall, developing scenarios requires the identification of the two most critical uncertainties (or drivers) in the topic of concern. But, if the two uncertainties act as proxies for one another, despite belonging to different conceptual categories, you would end up with similar stories.⁴
3. **Complete.** Scenarios do not provide precise details, leaving space for the reader to add them.⁵ However, it is important to ensure that no critical uncertainty (i.e., an uncertainty that does not subsume or act as a proxy for the primary axis drivers) has been overlooked.⁶
4. **Internally consistent.** Scenarios must be internally consistent, without contradictions in the scenario logic or the scenario outcomes. It is critical to remember that scenarios must describe what could happen and not what would be nice to happen.⁷

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- ¹ Brummell, A. & MacGillivray, G. Introduction to Scenarios. Scenarios to Strategy Inc. Retrieved from: <https://www.scenarios2strategy.com/pdf/Introduction%20to%20Scenarios%20and%20Scenario%20Planning.pdf>
- ² Rasmus, D. (2018). Scenario Planning: How To Test Scenarios. Retrieved from: <https://www.seriousinsights.net/scenario-planning-how-to-test-scenarios/>
- ³ Overseas Development Institute (ODI). (2009). Strategy Development: Scenario Testing and Visioning. Retrieved from: <https://www.odi.org/publications/5213-strategy-development-scenario-testing-and-visioning>
- ⁴ Rasmus, D. (2018). Scenario Planning: How To Test Scenarios. Retrieved from: <https://www.seriousinsights.net/scenario-planning-how-to-test-scenarios/>
- ⁵ Overseas Development Institute (ODI). (2009). Strategy Development: Scenario Testing and Visioning. Retrieved from: <https://www.odi.org/publications/5213-strategy-development-scenario-testing-and-visioning>
- ⁶ Rasmus, D. (2018). Scenario Planning: How To Test Scenarios. Retrieved from: <https://www.seriousinsights.net/scenario-planning-how-to-test-scenarios/>
- ⁷ Brummell, A. & MacGillivray, G. Introduction to Scenarios. Scenarios to Strategy Inc. Retrieved from: <https://www.scenarios2strategy.com/pdf/Introduction%20to%20Scenarios%20and%20Scenario%20Planning.pdf>